

The Motives for Prostitution Consumption Scale (MCPS)

1. Population and context

- **Target population:** Young people aged 18–29 years from the general population.
- **Context of use:** Academic research in the field of social psychology, gender studies, and attitudes toward prostitution and paid sex.

2. Instructions to participants

We present a series of statements about prostitution and about women in prostitution. Please indicate your degree of agreement or disagreement with each statement.

There are no right or wrong answers; we are only interested in general opinions. The most important thing is that you respond with your most sincere opinion.

3. Response format

All items are answered using a 6-point Likert-type scale ranging from: 1 = Strongly disagree; 2 = Disagree; 3 = Somewhat disagree; 4 = Somewhat agree; 5 = Agree; 6 = Strongly agree.

4. Items

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1. They seek enjoyment
 2. They feel lonely or have poor emotional relationships
 3. They are dissatisfied with their sexual relationships with their partner
 4. They seek variety or new experiences, to experiment or fulfil sexual fantasies
 5. They want to be with women who offer a different sexual experience
 6. They need sexual relations more frequently
 7. It is seen as a characteristic of masculinity or manhood
 8. It may be their only opportunity to have sex in a relationship
 9. They want to avoid commitments and have quick and easy sexual encounters
 10. They have physiological and sexual needs that must be satisfied
 11. They are young and developing their masculinity/sexuality
 12. It is a way to have intimate, affectionate, and close companionship through sex
 13. They seek intimacy, to be listened to, or understood
 14. They look for something more daring or risky in sex
 15. It is a way to celebrate something (business, parties, bachelor parties)
 16. They feel a sense of control or dominance that appeals to them
 17. They want to explore beyond the usual boundaries of sex
 18. They want to enjoy the “forbidden” sex acts, without social judgment
 19. They are addicts who cannot control themselves

20. It allows them to engage in sexual practices usually seen only in “porn”

5. Factor structure / Subscales

Scoring and subscales

The scale is composed of two motivational factors identified through exploratory factor analysis:

- **Factor 1. Experimentation, attraction, or forbidden sex acts**, composed of the following items: 4, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, and 20.
- **Factor 2. Sexual need, satisfaction, and companionship**, composed of the following items: 2, 3, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13.

For each factor, scores are calculated as the mean of the corresponding items, with higher scores indicating a greater degree of agreement with that motivational dimension.

6. Reverse-coded items

No items are reverse-coded.

7. Authorship and license

This questionnaire was developed by Dimitrova-Velikova, M., Terol-Cantero, M. C., Vázquez Rodríguez, C., and Martín-Aragón, M. as part of an academic research project. The scale is made available under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

8. Ethical note

The study was conducted in accordance with ethical standards and received approval from the Ethics Committee through the O.I.R. (Research Office Register: 191211112032; OIR; Reference: DCC.MMG.03.19) at Miguel Hernández University. The questionnaire was administered on a voluntary and anonymous basis for research purposes only, and all participants provided informed consent prior to participation